

Rural Finance and Agricultural Technology Adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Poorly functioning rural financial markets have been identified as a barrier that adversely influences farmers' technology adoption decisions. Focusing on four critical financial services (credit, insurance, savings, and mobile money), this study systematically reviews the evidence on their impact on agricultural technology adoption among rural farmers in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Following PRISMA 2020 guidelines, Scopus and 3ie databases were searched for relevant experimental, quasi-experimental, and rigorous econometric studies conducted in SSA, and complemented with a manual search through reference lists of identified articles. To ensure efficiency, distinct search strings were designed and utilized to identify studies related to the four financial services. From the 1254 studies identified through the search procedure, 30 studies met all the inclusion criteria specified after screening. Almost half (14) of the studies examined the impact of credit access, followed by insurance (8), savings (4), and mobile money (4). The review finds that access to credit, savings, and mobile money services consistently has a positive impact on rural farmers' agricultural technology adoption and investment behaviour. However, more research on the impact of mobile money and savings is needed, given the limited number of studies in SSA. Lastly, the impact of agricultural index insurance appears to be mixed. Consequently, we recommend additional research to establish its influence on farmers' technology adoption decisions.

Keywords: Rural finance, credit, index insurance, mobile money, savings, adoption

Introduction

Agriculture is a critical sector in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), playing a vital role in the region's economy and employment. It is the dominant

economic activity in the rural areas, where the majority of people live (World Bank, 2023). It is estimated that more than 60% of the region's workforce is engaged in agriculture, making it

the largest employer in the region (Osabohien *et al.*, 2019). It provides both direct employment for farmers (mostly smallholders) and indirect employment opportunities in related industries such as transportation, storage, and processing. However, most of the poor and food-insecure in the region are engaged in agriculture. This has made the sector the target of different interventions to bring about poverty alleviation and rural development based on agriculture-led growth strategies, particularly in the light of the Asian green revolution, which served as a foundation for the economic transformation of different Asian countries (Diao, Hazell, and Thurlow, 2010; de Janvry and Sadoulet, 2020).

de Janvry and Sadoulet (2020) succinctly outline four complementary pathways through which development could be achieved through agriculture, especially in SSA countries, which are dominated by smallholder farmers. The first pathway is the achievement of 'productivity growth in staple foods' through the adoption of modern technologies. The second pathway is 'asset building' by smallholder farmers through improved incomes resulting from increased productivity. The achievement of productivity in staple foods frees up resources (land, labour, and capital) to 'diversify towards high value crops'. All these culminate in increasingly complex value-added activities (such as processing) in the rural areas, thus leading to rural transformation. This crucial role of agriculture in rural development is established in empirical literature. Specifically, Ivanic and Martin (2018) and Ligon and Sadoulet (2018) demonstrate that agricultural productivity reduces poverty about two to three times more effectively than equivalent growth in the industrial and services sectors.

However, the results of the green revolution

aimed at increasing agricultural productivity in SSA have been largely disappointing (Voortman, 2013; Dawson, Martin, and Sikor, 2016; Till, 2021). Although the proportion of farmers using green revolution technologies (improved varieties, inorganic fertilizer, agrochemicals) has improved from the 1960s level, it still lags the rest of the world, as shown in Figures 1 and 2 (Sheahan and Barrett, 2017; Our World in Data, 2023a; Our World in Data, 2023b). Agricultural production is still largely characterized by traditional labour-intensive methods of production, relatively small, scattered plots, limited use of agricultural machinery and other technological innovations, as well as low adoption of improved varieties, agrochemicals, and fertilizers. All these have resulted in low agricultural productivity, insufficient food production to meet local demands, low farmer incomes, and a high incidence of food insecurity and poverty in the rural areas (OECD/FAO, 2016; Bjornlund, Bjornlund, and Van Rooyen, 2020).

Figure 3 illustrates the productivity gap between Africa and the rest of the world's regions using cereal yield in the past 60 years (Our World in Data, 2023c). While Africa averaged 1.63 tonnes per hectare (which is double what it produced 60 years ago), Asia and South America have almost quadrupled their productivity over the same period to produce 4.23 tonnes and 5.06 tonnes per hectare, respectively. One of the factors that has been identified as a key constraint to agricultural productivity and rural development is inadequate access to financial services in rural areas, i.e., rural finance markets are either missing or failing in SSA (Dillon and Barret, 2017). Agricultural production outcomes can, and are often affected by factors beyond the control of the farmer, climatic variables that

affect output and volatile food prices that affect their income.

Given the risk level and farmers' inability to pre-fund additional investment because they are mostly poor, rural farm households' decision on agricultural investment (including technology adoption), size of operation, crop mix, and labour utilization depend on the nature of financial services available to them (Conning and Udry, 2007; de Janvry and Sadoulet, 2020). Using data from five sub-Saharan countries, Dillon and Barrett (2017) argue that the absence of properly functioning rural financial markets is an important structural barrier limiting rural farm households' agricultural investment.

This review focuses on four critical financial services that constitute a robust rural financial market, namely credit, insurance, savings, and payment services, and their impact on agricultural technology adoption (World Bank, 2003; Biscaye *et al.*, 2015). Various studies have suggested that access to each of these services could positively affect rural farmers' risk behavior and adoption of new technologies through different pathways. Literature suggests that access to credit eases rural farmers' liquidity constraints, enabling them to invest in new agricultural technologies and better inputs (improved seed, fertilizer, agrochemicals, mechanization, land expansion among others) which translate to improved productivity, income and welfare for the farmers (Biscaye *et al.*, 2015; Adebayo *et al.*, 2022; Shepherd *et al.*, 2022).

Access to savings/deposit service could help farm households provide capital for farm investment by saving excess income, particularly after harvest, and accessing it as the need arises. Similarly, farmers can use their

savings to cover the operating costs associated with new technology, e.g., fuel costs or water charges associated with investment in a new irrigation system. Savings also improve farmers' chances of accessing credit through the availability of counterpart fund and/or collateral (built-up assets) (Biscaye *et al.*, 2015; Brune *et al.*, 2016).

Farmers are often unwilling to utilize agricultural credit to expand production and purchase improved inputs because of the inherent risk involved in the production process. In this context, agricultural insurance provides security in case of shocks that could otherwise wipe out their expected earnings and sink them further into poverty. Given that agricultural insurance allows rural farmers to transfer some of the risk to a third party, it could encourage them to adopt new technology (Ankrah *et al.*, 2021). Secondly, agricultural insurance makes it easier for credit institutions to provide loans for agriculture because it increases the farmers' probability of repayment, even when shocks occur (Baskaran and Maher, 2021). Furthermore, access to payment services connects rural farmers to the broader input and output market by reducing their reliance on physical cash-based transactions and lowering their transaction costs. Perhaps more importantly, it enables them to receive remittances from urban areas, which can be deployed to investment in better inputs and improved agricultural technology (Kikulwe *et al.*, 2014).

While the conceptual literature as outlined above largely agrees on the positive relationship between access to rural financial services and agricultural technology adoption, results from empirical studies in SSA are mixed about the relationship, necessitating a review to synthesize the results. Although there are

existing reviews on rural financial markets/services and technology adoption, they often focus broadly on the factors influencing technology adoption (Ruzzante, Labarta and Bilton, 2022), on only one financial service (Girma, 2022; Marr *et al.*, 2016), on one country (Girma, 2022) or on other welfare outcomes (Biscaye *et al.*, 2015).

In particular, the primary objective of this review was to assess the impact of these rural financial services on farmers' agricultural technology adoption. This study contributes to the literature on three fronts. First, this systematic review of empirical literature on the impact of four rural financial services (credit, insurance, savings, and payments) was conducted using the most recent Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Page *et al.*, 2021). Second, following Biscaye *et al.* (2015), the review focused on studies that utilized experimental, quasi-experimental, and econometric methods that accounted for endogeneity and self-selection problems that can bias impact estimates. Third, interactions between these financial services were accounted for; for instance, credit-linked insurance and payments linked savings, and their impacts on farmers' agricultural investment decisions. The findings of this review will provide an evidence base for formulating appropriate policy responses to reposition rural financial markets for more effectiveness in improving agricultural productivity and farmers' welfare. The rest of the review is organized as follows. The next section outlines the systematic literature search methodology, the third section reports the findings of the studies reviewed according to each financial service, and the last section identifies the gaps for further research and concludes the paper.

Methodology

Inclusion Criteria

Studies assessed to achieve the stated objective had to meet the following inclusion criteria. First, studies had to be carried out in one or more sub-Saharan countries. Secondly, the study had to be a full-length published journal article or working paper. Thirdly, the manuscripts had to be written in English. Thus, studies that were not carried out in sub-Saharan African countries, that were not journal articles or working papers (such as reviews, book chapters, research notes, etc.), and not written in English were excluded.

Search Protocol

A systematic literature search was conducted through the Scopus database and the International Initiative for Impact Evaluation (3ie) Development Evidence portal to retrieve relevant studies. This was complemented with manual searches through the reference lists of identified articles to ensure completeness. To ensure efficiency in identifying studies related to each of the four rural financial services under consideration (credit, insurance, savings, and mobile money), distinct search strings were designed and utilized. For instance, the search string (credit OR microfinance OR loan OR finance) AND (empiric* OR effect OR experiment OR trial OR rct OR impact) AND (technology AND adoption) AND (rural OR agricultural OR farm OR farmer OR smallholder) was used to retrieve studies related to credit and agricultural technology adoption, restricting the search results by the inclusion criteria (see other search strings in the Appendix A). The results from the two databases were exported to Mendeley reference software, and duplicate records were removed.

Screening Procedure

Screening was conducted in two stages following the PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page *et*

al., 2021). The titles and abstracts of identified records were screened by a single reviewer against the study objective, and those not relevant were removed outright. The full texts of the remaining studies were retrieved for further screening against additional inclusion criteria to ensure the quality of included studies. Although screening was conducted by a single reviewer for time efficiency (Waffenschmidt *et al.*, 2019; Haby *et al.*, 2016), the inclusion and exclusion criteria were clearly predefined and systematically applied, thereby reducing the likelihood of bias. First, studies had to report empirical research results; conceptual or simulated studies with no empirical analysis were excluded at this stage. Second, studies had to report on the impact of one or more of the four financial services under consideration on agricultural technology adoption as an objective. Furthermore, only studies that utilized experimental (randomized controlled trials), quasi-experimental (e.g., propensity score matching, regression discontinuity), or econometric regression-based methods (e.g., instrumental variable estimation, endogenous switching regressions) that accounted for endogeneity and self-selection problems were included to ensure unbiased impact estimates. In the end, the process yielded 30 research reports across the four financial services, out of the 1254 studies identified. Figure 4 presents the PRISMA flow diagram, while Tables 1 and 2 summarize the included research reports by the financial services.

Results and Discussion

Study selection

Study selection was systematically conducted using the outlined inclusion criteria for the search results generated by each of the four distinct search strings. Collectively, entering the search strings designed to elicit studies yielded

a total of 1254 studies. Twenty (20) duplicates were removed using Mendeley reference management software, and 1129 studies were excluded after initial screening using the title, abstract, and keywords. After reviewing the remaining 115 documents (105 from the databases and 10 from reference search), 85 studies were excluded based on the exclusion criteria outlined in the previous section. Specifically, 65 studies were excluded because they did not examine outcomes related to agricultural technology adoption. Furthermore, 12 studies were excluded due to methodological approaches that did not address endogeneity and self-selection problems, six were excluded for being conceptual rather than empirical in nature, and two did not focus on sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). In the end, 30 studies [credit (14), insurance (8), savings (4), and mobile money (4)] that met all the inclusion criteria were included in the review as presented in Figure 4. Tables 1 and 2 summarize the included research reports according to the financial services.

Description of included studies

Except for Abdallah (2016), which utilized data from nine SSA countries (namely Ghana, Nigeria, Malawi, Kenya, Tanzania, Ethiopia, Mozambique, Uganda, and Zambia), and Makate *et al* (2019), which analyzed data from Zimbabwe and Malawi, all the included studies were conducted in a single country. Figure 5 shows the distribution of the included studies (without the multi-country studies) across different countries in SSA. Eight of the studies were carried out in Ethiopia, four in Malawi, and three each in Ghana, Kenya, and Tanzania. As shown in Tables 1 and 2, 26 of the 30 studies (86.6%) were published as journal articles, while the rest are working papers. Furthermore, 15 studies (50.0%) were randomized controlled trials, 13 employed

rigorous econometric methods that controlled for endogeneity, and 2 applied quasi-experimental methods (propensity score matching).

Credit Access and Agricultural Technology Adoption

Most of the studies found a positive and significant relationship between credit access or provision and agricultural technology adoption across different SSA countries, although the impact of credit-linked insurance on technology adoption is mixed.

Standalone Agricultural Credit

Abate *et al* (2016) investigated the impact of institutional credit access (from microfinance institutions and finance cooperatives) on agricultural technology adoption and intensity of use, focusing on inorganic fertilizer and improved seed in Ethiopia. The study followed a quasi-experimental design, randomly selecting households from villages with no institutional credit provider (control group) and credit-using households in villages with either a microfinance institution (MFI) or a finance cooperative (FC) but not both (treatment group). On average, farmers with institutional credit access were 11% and 30% more likely to adopt fertilizer and improved seed, and used 51kg and 25kg of fertilizer and improved seed per hectare more than farmers with no credit access.

Furthermore, the heterogeneous impact of the institutional credit source was examined with interesting results. While the likelihood of fertilizer adoption was comparable across the two credit sources, the impact on intensity of use was very different. On average, farmers using credit from finance cooperatives used twice as much fertilizer per hectare as farmers who obtained credit from microfinance

institutions. In addition, farmers who obtained credit from FCs were far more likely to adopt improved seed (42% to 16%) and used five times more improved seed than farmers who obtained credit from MFIs. This difference in effectiveness could be because finance cooperatives typically have lower interest rates, greater accessibility, and less stringent requirements, since they rely more on social networks among closely linked members, compared to microfinance institutions that operate largely as scaled-down versions of formal commercial banks.

In a randomized controlled trial conducted in Mali, Beaman *et al* (2014) offered agricultural loans at the beginning of the planting season to women farmers' groups, with an agreement that it would be repaid after harvest. The authors report a positive and significant increase in fertilizer and agrochemicals expenditure, as well as total agricultural investment. Strikingly, all the loans were fully repaid at the end of the season. This provides evidence for the effectiveness of the group-lending/liability approach in typically closely knit rural areas, where the threat of losing social standing may be sufficient to enforce loan repayment (Fischer, 2013; Gallenstein, Flatnes, and Sam, 2020).

Amin *et al* (2022) estimated both the direct and spillover effects of credit access on the adoption of organic fertilizer, inorganic fertilizer, and pesticide among smallholder farmers in Tanzania. The authors find that while credit access increases farmers' likelihood of adopting inorganic fertilizer and pesticide by 16% and 9.6% respectively (direct effect), it also has a positive and significant spillover effect, i.e., farmers neighboring the adopters had a 22% higher likelihood of adopting inorganic fertilizer. Carter, Laajaj, and Yang (2021) also

report that credit, in the form of a discounted input voucher provided for a single season, increased fertilizer and improved seed adoption among farmers in Mozambique. Interestingly, the study reported that input use persisted in the following seasons when there was no discount.

Dillon and Tomaselli (2022) studied the impact of credit access on technology adoption by varying whether farmers got loans, the proportion of the input cost that farmers had to pay upfront (either 10 or 50%), and the timing of the offer (post-harvest or planting season). The authors report that farmers who got loans increased their purchase of inputs (fertilizer, pesticides, improved seeds) by 16% and 11.1% in treatment groups that paid 10% and 50% of the input cost upfront, respectively. Studies conducted in Ethiopia also confirmed that credit access positively influenced agricultural technology adoption (Tadesse, 2014; Tesfay, 2021) and intensity of input use (Tadesse, 2014).

Using data from nine SSA countries, Abdallah (2016) reported that about two-thirds (63%) of the farmers interviewed did not have access to credit. However, the author found that credit access increases farmers' likelihood of adopting the productivity-enhancing technologies (crop rotation, intercropping, improved fallowing, animal manure, tillage, green manure, grass strips, and agroforestry) considered in the study. Similarly, Makate *et al.* (2019) reported that joint access to extension and credit increases the probability of adopting improved legumes by 41.5%, conservative agriculture and intercropping by 41.5%, 50.2% and 6.2% respectively, in Zimbabwe and Malawi. Mohamed and Temu (2008) also report that access to formal credit had a positive impact on agricultural technology adoption among

farmers in Zanzibar, Tanzania.

Nonetheless, some studies report mixed results on the impact of credit on technology adoption, demonstrating that the impact can be heterogeneous based on certain characteristics. For instance, Liverpool and Winter-Nelson (2010) examined the heterogeneous impact of microcredit access on technology use among three farmer categories ('never poor', 'transitory poor', and 'always poor') using a three-wave panel data spanning 12 years in Ethiopia. They find that while credit access increases the likelihood of adopting pesticides for the 'never poor' category, its effect is insignificant among the 'transitory poor' and 'always poor' categories of farmers. This suggests that the poorest farmers prioritize basic consumption needs before agricultural investments, which should be considered when designing rural credit products.

Similarly, Nakano and Magezi (2020) conducted a randomized controlled trial to assess the impact of microcredit on technology adoption among rice farmers in two dissimilar irrigation schemes in Tanzania. Using a group lending approach, farmers in the treatment group were offered a mixed credit package comprising both cash and a fertilizer voucher. The authors found that the effect of credit on fertilizer adoption was not significant in the joint sample. However, disaggregated analysis by irrigation scheme revealed a significant and positive impact, with farmers in one scheme applying 14–37 kg more fertilizer than those in the control group.

Products Linking Credit and Insurance

Boucher, Carter, and Guirkinger (2008) argue that rural farmers may decide not to invest in new agricultural technologies and continue to

use low-risk traditional inputs due to risk rationing. This occurs when farmers voluntarily withdraw from the credit market because the disproportionate risk is shifted to the potential borrower and priced into the interest rate, especially when insurance is nonexistent. Thus, from a theoretical standpoint, linked credit and insurance products provide a way to overcome rural farmers' risk rationing and promote agricultural technology adoption. We report two studies that have attempted to empirically test this hypothesis in SSA.

In their influential study, Gine and Yang (2009) conducted a randomized control trial in Malawi, offering an insurance-backed loan for improved seed purchase to farmers in the treatment group and uninsured loans to the control group. Both categories of farmers were offered the loan at the beginning of the planting season and were to repay the loan after harvest. The authors find that the risk-rationing hypothesis did not hold – while 17.6% of the farmers took up the insurance-backed loan, nearly double (33.0%) of them opted for the uninsured loan.

However, a more recent study reported a contrasting result. Shukri *et al.* (2020) investigated the impact of an insurance-backed credit product offered to farmers through cooperative unions on farmers' agricultural technology adoption in Ethiopia. The authors report a 55% take-up rate for the product and an increase in the use of inorganic fertilizer (66.7%), improved seed (25.9%), and pesticide (15.7%) among the farmers who participated in the credit programme. These contrasting results highlight the need for further research on the impact of bundled credit and insurance products in SSA, particularly in contexts where farmers are familiar with the agricultural insurance products, to rule out the possibility of

farmers' reluctance to participate due to uncertainty about the reliability of the insurance product.

Agricultural Index Insurance and Agricultural Technology Adoption

All the included studies focused on agricultural index insurance, since conventional insurance proven ineffective in agriculture and often prohibitively expensive for both farmers and insurers for two main reasons; first, the high fixed cost of verifying individual losses for a large number of smallholder farmers in rural areas is unattractive and second, the possibility of moral hazard i.e., the possibility of a farmer becoming carefree in managing his farm in the hope of getting an insurance payment (Feed the Future, 2022). This limitation led to the promotion of agricultural index insurance, particularly with the development of more precise and sophisticated remote sensing technologies (Carter, Cheng, and Sarris, 2016).

Agricultural index insurance differs from conventional insurance in that it relies on an objective and transparent index of factors (most commonly rainfall or area yield) to predict individual losses and make payments if applicable. For instance, if a farmer purchases index insurance for drought (based on a rainfall index), he or she would receive a payout if the rainfall in their area falls below a certain threshold, regardless of whether they personally experienced crop losses. This means that the index must be sufficiently accurate to predict individual losses and minimize basis risk, i.e., the risk of farmers not receiving insurance payment despite losses or vice-versa. Agricultural index insurance eliminates the need to verify individual losses (which minimizes costs) and moral hazard, given that the index is based on factors that cannot be influenced by any individual (Syroka and

Reinecke, 2015; Carter *et al.*, 2017). Since its development, different studies have been conducted in SSA to investigate its impact on agricultural technology adoption, given its potential to help farmers overcome risk-rationing and boost farmers' agricultural investment for improved productivity. However, the findings of the studies have been mixed.

Elabed and Carter (2014), for instance, randomized cooperatives of cotton farmers into treatment groups that were offered an area yield index insurance at various discount levels and control groups that were not offered the insurance. The authors report a 30% take-up rate among the treatment group and observed an increase of 14% in cotton seed expenditure by insured cooperatives relative to uninsured cooperatives. In another study conducted in Ghana that offered rainfall index insurance at various discount levels (ranging from 0 to 100%) and cash grants, Karlan *et al* (2014) showed that insurance had a much higher positive effect on farmers' agricultural investment, particularly fertilizer expenditure, than capital (cash grant). Sibiko and Qaim (2020) also report that rainfall index insurance adoption had a positive impact on the quantity of fertilizer and improved seed used by maize farmers in Kenya. Furthermore, Haile, Tillesen, and Tirivayi (2020) demonstrate that adoption of weather index crop insurance reduced farmers' risk aversion, and find that farmers who adopted the index insurance were 60% more likely to use inorganic fertilizer. These findings support the view in the literature that insurance mitigates risk-rationing among resource-constrained smallholder farmers.

However, other studies did not find a positive impact of agricultural index insurance on agricultural technology adoption. For example,

Stoeffler *et al* (2022) report that while uptake of the area yield index insurance offered to cotton farmers in Burkina Faso was relatively high (46%), there was no significant difference in input use between insurance adopters and non-adopters. Wong *et al* (2020) also find that rainfall insurance had little to no significant effect on input use among smallholder farmers in Ethiopia. In Shukri *et al* (2020), the authors report that the adoption of rainfall index insurance did not significantly impact fertilizer and improved seed use among farmers in Ethiopia.

The heterogeneity in reported impacts of agricultural index insurance on technology adoption can be explained by several contextual and design-related factors. First, the delivery mechanism of insurance products appears to be critical. For example, both Shukri *et al.* (2020) and Elabed and Carter (2014), who reported relatively higher uptake and positive impacts on technology adoption, introduced the products through established farmer cooperatives. Farmer cooperatives may enhance trust by providing a credible platform for disseminating information about the insurance product, thereby improving both participation and adoption of agricultural technologies (Wossen *et al.*, 2017). This view is supported by the findings of Haile, Tillesen, and Tirivayi (2020), who show that access to adequate information about the mechanism and benefits of agricultural insurance significantly increased both insurance uptake and technology adoption.

Second, the design of the insurance product itself strongly influences its effectiveness. In Sibiko and Qaim (2020), the rainfall index insurance contract was structured to cover the full cost of insured inputs in the event of a shock, with payouts delivered immediately

after the shock occurred. This timeliness and reliability enabled affected farmers to replant and salvage the farming season, thereby encouraging increased adoption of improved inputs. By contrast, Stoeffler *et al.* (2022) attribute the lack of significant impact in Burkina Faso to farmers' low trust in insurers' willingness and capacity to pay, as well as delays in payout.

Finally, it is important to note the role of insurance premium subsidies in driving observed impacts. Several studies that reported positive effects on technology adoption, such as Elabed and Carter (2014) and Karlan *et al.* (2014), relied on subsidized premiums to encourage uptake among farmers unfamiliar with insurance products. This raises the possibility that the observed impacts are partly driven by the implicit financial transfer embedded in the subsidy, rather than the insurance mechanism itself. Thus, the positive impact on technology adoption has to be interpreted cautiously, especially when extrapolating these results to real-world contexts where farmers would face actuarially fair premium rates. These findings suggest that while index insurance has the potential to facilitate technology adoption, its effectiveness depends on the delivery mechanism, adequate information about the product among farmers, and the credibility and timeliness of payouts.

Access to Savings Services and Agricultural Technology Adoption

Access to savings services is an important component of rural financial services as it helps farmers maintain a degree of control over their current spending and conserve financial resources for future expenditure. Studies have examined the impact of access to savings through the more common and often informal Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLAs),

formal savings products, and more recently, mobile money accounts on technology adoption.

Formal Savings

Brune *et al.* (2016) examine the impact of formal savings access on agricultural input investment among tobacco farmers in Malawi, who typically receive cash payments for their output. In a randomized controlled trial, both farmers in the treatment and control groups were encouraged to save for future agricultural input purchases. However, only those in the treatment group were assisted in opening a bank savings account into which their next sales proceeds were deposited. The authors found significant increases in savings and agricultural input purchases (13.3%) relative to the control group.

Village Savings and Loans Associations

VSLAs operate by members pooling their savings into a common fund, which can then be used to provide loans to interested members at agreed-upon interest rates. Members access their savings and the interest earned on them at the end of the savings cycle. In a randomized controlled trial in Malawi, Ksoll *et al.* (2016) find that farming households in the treatment group (VSLA participation) were more likely to utilize fertilizer in their farming operation. Similarly, Dagunga *et al.* (2020) find that participation in VSLAs increased the likelihood of adopting *Zai* technology in northern Ghana. These findings suggest that access to savings services helps farmers conserve financial resources and increase their agricultural input investment over a planning horizon.

Products linking Savings and Mobile money

Batista and Vicente (2020) examined the effect of access to savings through a mobile money account on fertilizer adoption among farmers in

rural Mozambique using a randomized controlled trial. All farmers in the sample were assisted in opening a mobile money account, given practical training on how to operate it (with trial transactions), and educated about fertilizer use for their farm operations. Farmers in the treatment group were offered a 20% interest (paid with fertilizer) on their average savings in the mobile money account, while those in the control group did not. The authors found that savings increased significantly among the treatment group relative to the control group, but the difference became insignificant in the following seasons when the fertilizer incentive was not offered. Furthermore, access to savings had a positive impact on technology adoption: fertilizer adoption and intensity of use increased by 34-36% and 13.8-14.6kg, respectively among the treatment group relative to the control group. The study findings show that farmers' savings behaviour depends not only on the availability of the financial service, but also on its value proposition (incentives) relative to alternative uses of funds.

Mobile Money and Agricultural Technology Adoption

Mobile money is an innovative financial service for sending and receiving payments, which leverages mobile telecommunications' superior penetration in rural areas and is increasingly being adopted across sub-Saharan Africa. It contributes positively to rural household welfare by facilitating remittances from urban migrant workers, easing liquidity constraints, and enabling agricultural technology adoption (Peprah, Oteng, and Sebu, 2020).

Kirui *et al* (2013) and Kikulwe, Fischer, and Qaim (2014) explore the relationship between mobile money services and agricultural input use in Kenya, where mobile money was first

introduced in SSA in 2007. Using three matching techniques, Kirui *et al* (2013) show that farmers using mobile money services invested significantly more (\$42) in agricultural inputs and had a higher level of commercialization (37%) than farmers who did not use mobile money. Kikulwe, Fischer, and Qaim (2014) also find that farmers using mobile money services spent significantly more on agricultural technologies such as pesticides (\$15) and organic fertilizer (\$30) on average.

Given the spread of mobile money across SSA since 2007, other studies have explored its effect on technology adoption in other countries more recently. Focusing on inorganic fertilizer and herbicide adoption, Abdul-Rahaman and Abdulai (2022) examine the impact of mobile money adoption on technology adoption among rice farmers in Ghana. They find that mobile money has been adopted by 55.0% of the sampled farmers, and that its adoption increases herbicide and fertilizer use by 13% and 18% respectively. Tabetando *et al* (2022) also demonstrate that maize farmers who use mobile money services are more likely to adopt improved seeds and fertilizer by 8.2% and 11% respectively.

Conclusion

This systematic review concludes that access to rural financial services is a critical driver of agricultural technology adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa. The evidence consistently shows that access to credit, savings services, and mobile money has a positive impact on farmers' decisions to adopt and invest in technologies like improved seeds and fertilizer. The effectiveness of credit is enhanced by designs that align with agricultural seasons and leverage social structures like group lending. Similarly, community-based savings groups (VSLAs) and mobile money platforms provide vital

mechanisms for farmers to manage resources and reduce transaction costs. In contrast, the impact of agricultural index insurance remains mixed and highly dependent on contextual factors like delivery through trusted institutions, the design of reliable payout mechanisms, and the frequent use of subsidies, which questions its long-term sustainability. Therefore, while credit, savings, and mobile money are clear enablers, the role of insurance requires further research focused on developing sustainable, farmer-centric products that build trust and effectively mitigate risk. Future efforts should prioritize designing financial products that are tailored to the specific cashflow and risk management needs of smallholder farmers to unlock agricultural productivity in the region.

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APPENDIX A: Search Protocols

Agricultural Insurance Search Protocol

TITLE-ABS-KEY (insurance AND weather OR micro OR area-based OR rain* OR livestock OR index AND empiric* OR experiment OR trial OR rct OR impact)

Mobile Money Search Protocol

TITLE-ABS-KEY (mobile AND money) AND (empiric* OR effect OR experiment OR trial OR rct OR impact) AND (technology AND adoption) AND (rural OR agricultural OR farm OR farmer OR smallholder)

Savings Search Protocol

TITLE-ABS-KEY (saving* OR deposit) AND (empiric* OR effect OR experiment OR trial OR rct OR impact) AND (technology AND adoption) AND (rural OR agricultural OR farm OR farmer OR smallholder)

Figure 1: Fertilizer use per hectare (1961-2019)

Figure 2: Pesticide use per hectare (1990-2019)

Figure 3: Cereal Yield Comparison (1961-2020)

***Note: n1 = Insurance; n2 = Credit; n3 = Savings; n4 = Mobile money**

Figure 4: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for identification of studies

Table 1: Summary of reviewed studies – Credit and Savings

Author name	Publication year	Publication type	Country	Methodology	Sample size	Impact
Credit						
Abate <i>et al</i>	2016	Journal article	Ethiopia	PSM	817	Positive
Abdallah	2016	Journal article	Nine SSA countries	IV-2SLS	4992	Positive
Amin <i>et al</i>	2022	Working Paper	Tanzania	Spatially lagged Probit model	1712	Positive
Beaman <i>et al</i>	2014	Working Paper	Mali	RCT	6807	Positive
Carter, Laajaj and Yang	2021	Journal article	Mozambique	RCT	514	Positive
Dillon and Tomaselli	2023	Working Paper	Mali	RCT	140 villages	Positive
Liverpool and Winter-Nelson	2010	Journal article	Ethiopia	Conditional fixed effect logit	1477	Mixed
Makate <i>et al</i>	2019	Journal article	Zimbabwe, Malawi	IPWRA	1173	Positive
Mohamed and Temu	2008	Journal article	Tanzania	Switching the regression model	750	Positive
Nakano and Magezi	2020	Journal article	Tanzania	RCT	412	Mixed
Tadesse	2014	Journal article	Ethiopia	IV-2SLS	278	Positive
Tesfay	2021	Journal article	Ethiopia	Conditional Random effect logit	1412	Positive
<i>Credit and Insurance</i>						
Gine and Yang	2009	Journal article	Malawi	RCT	800	Negative
Shukri <i>et al.</i>	2020	Journal article	Ethiopia	RCT	934	Positive
<i>Total</i>	14					
Savings						
Batista and Vicente	2020	Journal article	Mozambique	RCT	588	Positive
Brune <i>et al</i>	2016	Journal article	Malawi	RCT	3150	Positive
Dagunga <i>et al</i>	2020	Journal article	Ghana	IV-3SLS	400	Positive
Ksoll <i>et al</i>	2016	Journal article	Malawi	RCT	1715	Positive
<i>Total</i>	4					

Table 2: Summary of reviewed studies – Insurance and Mobile money

Author name	Publication year	Publication type	Country	Methodology	Sample size	Impact
Insurance						
Elabed and Carter	2014	Working paper	Mali	RCT	981	Positive
Gine and Yang	2009	Journal article	Malawi	RCT	800	Negative
Haile <i>et al</i>	2020	Journal article	Ethiopia	Endogenous switching regression	240	Positive
Karlan <i>et al</i>	2014	Journal article	Ghana	RCT	502	Positive
Shukri <i>et al.</i>	2020	Journal article	Ethiopia	RCT	934	NS
Sibiko and Qaim	2020	Journal article	Kenya	IV-2SLS	386	Positive
Stoeffler <i>et al</i>	2022	Journal article	Burkina Faso	RCT	1015	NS
Wong <i>et al</i>	2020	Journal article	Ethiopia	RCT	1100	NS
<i>Total</i>	8					
Mobile money						
Abdul-Rahaman and Abdulai	2022	Journal article	Ghana	2SLS estimation	421	Positive
Kikulwe <i>et al</i>	2014	Journal article	Kenya	Panel Fixed effect	320	Positive
Kirui <i>et al</i>	2013	Journal article	Kenya	PSM	379	Positive
Tabetando <i>et al</i>	2022	Journal article	Uganda	IV estimation	781	Positive
<i>Total</i>	4					

Figure 4: Distribution of studies by Country